

Design Details

Design Application Number:

6406959

Filing Date (Provisional):

24 November 2024

Defer Registration:

No

Design Title:

ME AT CAMPUS: Adaptive Workflow Orchestration Using Neurophysiological Data in Enterprise Resource Planning Systems

Additional Description:

A graphical user interface for resource management comprising integrated neurophysiological data visualization and adaptive workflows.